

Studies on the Dissociation Constants of 2,2'-Dipyridyl and its Iron(II) Complex in Ethanol-Water Mixtures

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Dissociation constants of 2,2'-dipyridyl and its iron(II) complex have been studied in different mixed solvents containing 8-87 wt. % of ethanol. The results are discussed in the light of our present knowledge on ion-solvent interactions and solvent basicity.

IN continuation of studies on the dissociation constants of the ligands and their complexes in mixed solvents¹⁻⁴, we report in this communication the results of our investigations on the dissociation constants of the 'isoelectric' reactions of the type

in different ethanol-water solvents. This may enable us to get information and insight regarding the different types of interactions in mixed solvents.

Experimental

Absolute ethanol was treated with excess of calcium oxide, kept overnight and distilled. Middle fraction was collected for use. The traces of water, if any, in the organic solvents were neglected. The solvents were utilised within 24 hours.

The chemicals were of E. Merck's reagent grade.

Ferrous ammonium sulphate (G.R.-E.M.) solution was prepared by dissolving the weighed amount of the chemical in known quantity of HClO₄ (G.R.-E.M.). The purity of the ferrous ammonium sulphate was checked by estimation of the iron-content analytically with standard potassium dichromate in the usual way. The solution was utilised within several hours. For each set of measurement freshly prepared solution was used.

The solution of dipyridyl was prepared by directly weighing the reagent (G.R.-E.M.) and dissolving in the appropriate mixed solvents.

Double-distilled water from all glass distilling set was used for preparing the solutions.

In our measurements of the dissociation constants of 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-dipyridyl in mixed solvents by spectrophotometric method, it has been

found that the accuracy of determination of *pK* ultimately depends on the accuracy of the measurement of H⁺ ions in mixed solvents.

We, therefore, preferred to determine the dissociation constants of dipyridyl in ethanol-water mixtures by *pH*-titration.

To determine the *pK*-values by *pH*-titration, definite amounts of the ligand were taken in a number of volumetric flasks, acidified to different extents (30% to 70%) with known quantities of perchloric acid and the meter-readings were taken. The experiments were repeated with different concentrations (conc. range—5 × 10⁻³—1 × 10⁻² *M*) of the ligand.

The addition of Fe²⁺ ion to dipyridyl gave an intense red colouration with an absorption maximum at 524 nm (absorption maximum shifts to 522 nm in mixed solvents when the organic solvent content is high). The o.d. was found to change with H⁺ ion concentration without, however, changing the absorption maximum. The intensity became maximum at about *pH* 5.

Under our experimental conditions, Fe dipy₃²⁺ had been assumed to be the sole species formed without any Fe dipy₂²⁺ and Fe dipy₂³⁺.

Complete complexation in ethanol-water mixtures (i.e., conversion of Fe²⁺ into Fe dipy₃²⁺) required considerably greater amount of the ligand (about 10 fold or more) as indicated from the constancy in the o.d. readings containing a definite amount of Fe²⁺ ion and different concentrations of the ligand.

The extinction coefficients of ferrodiiin (the name we use for tris-dipyridyl complex of Fe²⁺ ion at 520 nm, 522 nm and 530 nm were determined from o.d. readings of solutions containing 10 to 20 fold excess of ligand to known amounts of ferrous ion where complete conversion of Fe²⁺ to Fe dipy₃²⁺ took place.

The extinction coefficients in different mixed solvents are given in Table I.

For the determination of stability constants of ferrodiiin in mixed solvents, o.d.'s of solutions contain-

ing different amounts of Fe²⁺ ion (concn. range 8–20 × 10⁻⁵M) and dipyriddy (concn. range 8–20 × 10⁻⁵M) were measured at 520, 522 and 530 nms.

TABLE 1—EXTINCTION COEFFICIENTS OF FERRODIIN COMPLEX AT DIFFERENT PERCENTAGES OF AQUEOUS ETHANOLIC SOLUTIONS

Temperature = 25°

Percentage of ethanol by wt.	Extinction coefficient at 520 nm	Extinction coefficient at 522 nm	Extinction coefficient at 530 nm
8.0	8483 ± 8	8518 ± 9	8270 ± 3
16.4	8530 ± 11	8572 ± 10	8351 ± 4
25.3	8600 ± 6	8644 ± 7	8400 ± 6
34.4	8790 ± 12	8840 ± 14	8558 ± 7
44.0	8858 ± 9	8908 ± 8	8608 ± 7
54.1	8663 ± 4	8718 ± 8	8300 ± 9
64.7	8613 ± 6	8663 ± 4	8243 ± 8
76.0	8316 ± 7	8367 ± 6	8050 ± 17
87.6	7758 ± 8	7800 ± 7	7441 ± 8

The pHs ranged from 2.80–3.65.

The concentrations of the complex were determined from o.d. readings and extinction coefficient values at these wavelengths. The concentrations of the complex came out to be almost equal at these wavelengths (±0.2%). For the calculation of equilibrium constant for the reaction (2), the average values of the complex obtained from measurements at three wavelengths were taken.

The weight percentages of the organic solvents in mixed solvents were calculated from the known amount of two solvents by volume and their densities at 25°. The reliability of this method of preparing a solvent mixture of given weight composition was checked by determining the densities of mixed solvents and comparing with the reported density values⁶. A slight disagreement was noted. This may be due to traces of water present in the organic solvent.

The dielectric constant values were calculated from the data given by Akerlöf and Short⁷.

Spectrophotometric readings were taken with a Beckman DU Spectrophotometer maintained at 25°. The pH-meter readings were taken with a Cambridge-bench type battery operated pH-meter.

Results

Dissociation constants of dipyriddyinium ion :

The thermodynamic dissociation constants K_T for the equilibrium

is represented by

$$K_T = \frac{a_A \times a_{H^+}}{a_{AH^+}} = \frac{C_A \times C_{H^+}}{C_{AH^+}} \times \frac{f_A \times f_{H^+}}{f_{AH^+}} \quad \dots (5)$$

Since the ionic strengths of the solutions were low (in the range 1.5–7.0 × 10⁻³), $\frac{f_A \times f_{H^+}}{f_{AH^+}}$ can be taken to unity. Even in concentrated solutions, $f_{H^+} = f_{AH^+}$ (due to same charge types and f_A equal to unity). Slight deviation may arise due to different ion-size parameter of H⁺ and AH⁺ ions.

Thus,

$$pK_T = pH + \log \frac{C_{AH^+}}{C_A} \\ = [B] + \log U_H + \log \frac{C_{AH^+}}{C_A} \quad \dots (6)$$

[B] = meter-readings in mixed solvents.

log U_H = correction factor in mixed solvents.

log $\frac{C_{AH^+}}{C_A}$ was determined from the fraction of neutralisation.

The glass electrodes in different mixed solvents were calibrated in the same way as described before⁸⁻¹⁰ and log U_H (correction factor) values were determined before each set of measurements. The results are given in Table 2.

Discussion constants of ferrous-tris-dipyriddy complex :

The equilibrium between ferrodin and a strong acid may be represented as

Thus,

$$K_a = \frac{f_{Fe^{2+}} \times C_{\text{dipy}H^+}^3}{C_{Fe \text{ dipy}_3^{2+}} \times C_{H^+}^3} \times \frac{f_{Fe^{2+}} \times f_{\text{dipy}H^+}^3}{f_{Fe \text{ dipy}_3^{2+}} \times f_{H^+}^3} \\ = K_c \times \frac{f_{Fe^{2+}} \times f_{\text{dipy}H^+}^3}{f_{Fe \text{ dipy}_3^{2+}} \times f_{H^+}^3} \quad \dots (8)$$

If, $f_{Fe^{2+}} = f_{Fe \text{ dipy}_3^{2+}}$ and $f_{\text{dipy}H^+} = f_{H^+}$, K_c becomes equal to K_a . But since dipy H⁺ is likely to have much larger size it may be that $f_{\text{dipy}H^+} \neq f_{H^+}$, which would need an accurate determination of $f_{\text{dipy}H^+}$.

Accurate determination of the thermodynamic dissociation constants are possible only in dilute solutions where activity coefficients are unity.

In concentrated solutions the determinations of activity coefficients are difficult. Theoretical equations like Debye-Hückel equation or semi-empirical equations like Davies equation are of limited use and that too in dilute solutions. Deviations are appreciable in concentrated solutions. The complexity increases much more in mixed solvents. The orientation of the solvent molecules around the ions are not known and it is difficult to know the extent of solute-solvent interactions in mixed solvents. In

TABLE 2

Wt. % of ethanol	$1 \times 10^3 D$	Mole fraction of ethanol	K_T for reaction (1)	K_a for reaction (2)		$K_a \times K_T^3$ fraction (3)	
				Using observed hydrogen ion concentration after proper correction	Using calculated hydrogen ion concentration	Using observed hydrogen ion concentration after proper correction	Using calculated hydrogen ion concentration
0.0	1.27	—	$3.34(\pm 0.15) \times 10^{-5}$	$7.56(\pm 0.27) \times 10^{-5}$	$4.36(\pm 0.15) \times 10^{-5}$	2.81×10^{-16}	1.62×10^{-16}
8.0	1.35	0.033	$6.31(\pm 0.30) \times 10^{-5}$	$4.48(\pm 0.16) \times 10^{-5}$	$2.51(\pm 0.07) \times 10^{-5}$	1.12×10^{-17}	6.30×10^{-18}
16.4	1.42	0.071	$9.12(\pm 0.70) \times 10^{-5}$	$2.85(\pm 0.12) \times 10^{-5}$	$1.56(\pm 0.06) \times 10^{-5}$	2.16×10^{-17}	1.18×10^{-17}
25.3	1.53	0.117	$1.23(\pm 0.15) \times 10^{-4}$	$1.55(\pm 0.06) \times 10^{-5}$	$7.01(\pm 0.25) \times 10^{-6}$	2.88×10^{-17}	1.30×10^{-17}
34.4	1.71	0.170	$1.91(\pm 0.25) \times 10^{-4}$	$2.03(\pm 0.12) \times 10^{-5}$	$7.86(\pm 0.35) \times 10^{-6}$	1.40×10^{-16}	5.48×10^{-17}
44.0	1.90	0.235	$3.31(\pm 0.60) \times 10^{-4}$	$1.33(\pm 0.05) \times 10^{-5}$	$6.03(\pm 0.30) \times 10^{-6}$	4.83×10^{-16}	2.19×10^{-16}
54.1	2.14	0.315	$6.31(\pm 1.30) \times 10^{-4}$	$5.03(\pm 0.25) \times 10^{-6}$	$2.84(\pm 0.15) \times 10^{-6}$	1.25×10^{-15}	7.13×10^{-16}
64.7	2.45	0.418	$7.94(\pm 2.20) \times 10^{-4}$	$6.10(\pm 0.30) \times 10^{-6}$	$3.97(\pm 0.20) \times 10^{-6}$	3.05×10^{-15}	1.98×10^{-15}
76.0	2.92	0.554	$1.29(\pm 0.40) \times 10^{-3}$	$4.10(\pm 0.30) \times 10^{-7}$	$2.87(\pm 0.10) \times 10^{-7}$	8.73×10^{-16}	6.14×10^{-16}
87.6	3.41	0.734	$1.62(\pm 0.50) \times 10^{-3}$	$8.55(\pm 0.40) \times 10^{-8}$	$5.90(\pm 0.30) \times 10^{-8}$	2.58×10^{-16}	2.50×10^{-16}

mixed solvents it is convenient to separate activity coefficients of the i th species into factors

$$\gamma_i = m\gamma_i \cdot s\gamma_i^{11} \quad \dots (9)$$

The 'salt-effect' $s\gamma_i$ varies with the solute concentration. Simple Debye-Hückel equation with appropriate allowance for the effect of altering the dielectric constant of the medium S can be used to estimate $s\gamma_i$ when the ionic species are involved. The limitations which affect the actual determination of activity coefficients in aqueous solutions would be much more in mixed or non-aqueous solutions. In dilute solutions $s\gamma_i \rightarrow 0$ and thus only the "medium effects" with which we are concerned in the study of the dissociation constants will be involved.

In view of the above facts the present work has been carried out in solutions of μ of the order of $10^{-3}M$ (ionic strengths were of the order of 4.0×10^{-4} to $3.3 \times 10^{-3}M$) where it is reasonable to assume $f_{Fe^{2+}} = f_{Fe dipys^{2+}}$ and $f_{dipys H^+} = f_{H^+}$ (slight discrepancy, if any, may be neglected).

Thus K_c becomes equal to thermodynamic equilibrium constant K_a .

Now

$$(\text{dipy } H^+) = (\text{dipy})_{Total} - 3(\text{Fe dipys}^{2+}) - (\text{dipy}) \quad \dots (10)$$

$(\text{dipy } H^+)$ is calculated where necessary from (6) taking appropriate pK values from Table 2.

The concentration of Fe^{2+} is calculated from the relation

$$[Fe^{2+}]_{free} = (Fe^{2+})_{Total} - (Fe \text{ dipys}^{2+}) \quad \dots (11)$$

The measurement of the hydrogen ion concentrations of the solutions containing the complexes and $\text{dipy } H^+$ are difficult.

We have calculated the H^+ ion concentrations in the solutions and compared it with the H^+ ion concentrations obtained from meter-readings after appropriate corrections in mixed solvents.

It has been observed that there is considerable deviation between the experimental and calculated values which, of course, increases with increasing percentage of mixed solvents and with increasing H^+ ion concentrations. The deviation is justifiable in view of the decreased sensitivity of the electrodes and unknown 'medium effects' as well as 'salt effects' of the different ions present in mixed solvents. We have kept the ionic strength particularly low ($1.4-3.3 \times 10^{-3}M$) so that the 'salt effect' is negligible though it may have some effect specially when the dielectric constant is low.

The importance of the accurate determination of H^+ ion concentrations in determining K_a is apparent from equation (8) and can be well-understood from the fact that the slight error in the measurement of H^+ ions (± 0.04) will have profound effect on the K_a value and the error in K_a values will be about $\pm 50\%$.

The equilibrium constants for the reaction (2) using calculated H^+ ion concentration as well as using measured H^+ ion concentrations from pH -meter readings with appropriate corrections in different mixed solvents are given in Table 2. The two sets of equilibrium constant values indicate the extent of deviation which one can have in such measurements.

The equilibrium constants

$$K = \frac{[Fe^{2+}][dipy]^3}{[Fe \text{ dipys}^{2+}]} \quad \dots (12)$$

for the reaction

in different solvents are given by

$$K = K_a \times K_T^3 \quad \dots (14)$$

The values are given in Table 2.

Discussions

The *pK* values of 2,2'-dipyridyl in different percentages of ethanol-water mixtures show the following generalisations :

- a) The *pK* values are found to be linear function of ethanol by weight (upto about 70%).
- b) The plot of *pK* against mole-fraction (upto about 0.4) of organic solvents is linear within error limits similar to the observations by Uiter and others^{12,13}.
- c) The plot of *pK* against 1/*D* in different ethanol-water mixtures is also linear upto about *D* = 45.¹⁴

The accurate determination of H⁺ ion concentrations is of paramount importance in the determination of *pK* values. Deviations at higher percentages of organic solvents may be due to the fact that at the high percentages of organic solvents, the H⁺ ion values from *pH*-meter readings may be inaccurate due to

- 1) high liquid-junction potential of uncertain magnitude,
- 2) low sensitivity of the glass electrode,
- 3) solute-solvent interactions may be high in this region.

The *pK* values in water obtained from different type of extrapolations are (a) 4.35, (b) 4.32 and (c) 4.26. Thus it is apparent that the extrapolated

In general, deviations are larger in ethanol-water mixtures.

Similar extrapolations of *pK_a* and *pK* values for reactions (2) and (3) against weight percentages, mole-fractions of the organic solvent and against 1/*D* are made with limited success. The deviations are large in 25.3 wt. % of organic solvent. It has been already pointed out that slight error in the measurement of H⁺ ions (± 0.04) will have profound effect on *K_a* and *K*. Moreover, the solute-solvent interactions in mixed solvents with ions and complexes of higher valence types may have influence on the equilibrium constants. Considering the limitations, the results can be regarded to be in good agreement.

ΔpK for the reactions (1), (2) and (3) are given in Table 3.

All these reactions are "isoelectric" in character. Therefore, the change in "dielectric constant" should have little effect on the reactions except in little changes in free energy resulting from the small differences of the radii of ions. Similar to the observations of Bates and others^{15,16} in case of acids of the type $\text{AH}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{A} + \text{H}^+$, present studies strongly indicate that the electrostatic terms resulting from the changes in dielectric constant with solvent composition is of minor importance to explain the solvent effect, the major term being solute-solvent interaction.

In a binary solvent mixture consisting of water and alcohol (RH) molecules, both of which can accept and donate protons, a general formulation can be made in terms of the law of mass action, activity coefficients and medium effects.

A knowledge of the proton-exchange constant *K_p* for the reaction

is essential for the proper understanding of the reactions.

TABLE 3— $\Delta pK = p_s K - p_w K$, IN AQUEOUS ETHANOLIC SOLUTION

Wt. % of ethanol	ΔpK for the reaction $\text{Dipy H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Dipy} + \text{H}^+$	ΔpK for the reaction $\text{Fe}^{2+} + 3\text{Dipy H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Fe}(\text{Dipy})_3^{2+} + 3\text{H}^+$	ΔpK for the reaction $\text{Fe}(\text{Dipy})_3^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Fe}^{2+} + 3\text{Dipy}$
8.0	-0.27	0.23	-0.58
16.4	-0.43	0.43	-0.86
25.3	-0.56	0.69	-0.99
34.4	-0.75	0.57	-1.68
44.0	-0.99	0.76	-2.21
54.1	-1.27	1.18	-2.63
64.7	-1.37	1.09	-3.01
76.0	-1.58	2.27	-2.47
87.6	-1.68	3.10	-1.94

pK values come out to be the same within experimental error whatever might be the type of extrapolations. However, the *pK* values thus obtained are considerably lower than those obtained from similar extrapolations in methanol-water mixtures [(a) 4.54, (b) 4.48 and (c) 4.47] or from *pK* value in water (4.47) determined spectrophotometrically.

Treating mixed solvents as a single solvent *S*, the apparent dissociation constant for the reaction

can be expressed in terms of *K_p* and the dissociation constant ω^K referred to pure solvent by the equation¹⁵

$$K = \omega^K (1 + 1/K_p).$$

However, in view of the deficiency of our knowledge of K_p , the significance of which is not always meaningful¹⁷, we are not in a position to throw much light on the solvent-basicity, solute-solvent interaction and thus on ΔpK_{nonei} .

One of the reasons we ascribe for the decrease in pK values for the reaction of the type $AH^+ \rightleftharpoons A + H^+$ may be the increase in the solubility of A and thus the greater tendency of A to go in organic solvents leading to greater dissociation of AH^+ . This together with the difference in solvational properties of H^+ and $dipy H^+$ would be responsible for the change in pK values. In case of reaction (2), $Fe(dipy)_3^{2+}$ may be assumed to be little solvated due to bigger ion-size parameter, the changes in pK values would depend on solvational properties of Fe^{2+} , H^+ and $dipy H^+$ in different mixed solvents whereas in case of reaction (3), the changes in pK would depend on the solvational property of Fe^{2+} ion and solubilities of $dipy$ and $Fe(dipy)_3^{2+}$.

It is not clear, however, what will be the effect of solvents on different ions like Fe^{2+} , H^+ , $dipy H^+$ etc. and whether the ions are solvated by organic solvents or water or both.

Some other salient features which need mention and explanation are :

1) We are unable to see any minimum in ΔpK values for the reaction (1) though a minimum in the pK values is generally observed in about 80 wt.% of ethanol¹⁵. However, the deviations are pronounced at about 70 wt.% and onwards. We have also reservations regarding our values at two highest percentages of organic solvents.

2) For the reaction (2), the pK_a increases with increase in alcohol concentration and reaches a maximum at about 54.1 wt.% ethanol.

3) The pK values for reaction (3) decreases and reaches minimum at 65 wt.% of ethanol.

4) The extinction coefficient of the complex increases and reaches a maximum at about 44 wt.% of ethanol and then decreases.

In view of the paucity of data regarding metallic complexes in mixed solvents, it is very difficult to speculate the reasons for the observed changes in mixed solvents.

5) From the calculated and experimental H^+ ion concentrations of solutions containing the same concentrations of H^+ ion, Fe^{2+} ion and ligand molecules it has been observed that the minimum in H^+ ion concentrations is obtained at about 65 wt.% of ethanol.

This is quite likely as the 'correction factor' is seen to be highest at about 65 wt.% of ethanol¹⁰.

From the result, it is reasonable to believe that the basicity is maximum in this region. The observation is in line with the observations of Popovych and co-workers¹⁸⁻²¹.

It is important to note that the 'medium effect' for the proton, $\log m\gamma_H$ estimated by Popovych and

co-workers is negative in ethanol-water mixtures containing 10 to 98 wt.% ethanol and passes through a minimum at 60 wt.% suggesting maximum basicity at 60 wt.%.

Braude and Stern²² observed a similar variation in solvent basicity from the behaviour of the acidity function H_0 in ethanol-water mixtures and maximum solvent basicity at equimolar solvent composition.

In order to throw more light, it is necessary to divide ΔpK into ΔpK_{el} and ΔpK_{nonei} as $\Delta pK = \Delta pK_{el} + \Delta pK_{nonei}$. The knowledge of ΔpK_{el} is thus essential to calculate ΔpK_{nonei} .

ΔpK_{el} can be calculated using modified Born's equations^{23,24}, if we know the accurate values of the radii of the different ions. The free energy of transfer of free base is also necessary. In view of our inadequate knowledge of the accurate values of radii of the ions and due to the limitations of the method of evaluating ΔpK_{el} , ΔpK_{nonei} of the mixed solvents were not calculated. But for the 'isoelectric' reactions of the type (1), (2) and (3), ΔpK_{el} can be assumed to be almost constant as a first approximation throughout the solvent composition. Thus, the changes in pK represent primarily the change of pK_{nonei} , which is governed to a large extent by solute-solvent interactions and the results indicate that the solute-solvent interactions are maximum in the region 60-80 wt.% of ethanol.

The results can also be explained by the fact that the ions are firmly held by the water molecules, the addition of a second solvent first alters the secondary solvational layer. The ion-solvent interaction in case of alcohol water mixtures are explained in terms of hydrogen-bonding superimposed on the ion-solvent interactions and it is known that the hydrogen-bonding capability is enhanced by equilibrium

Assuming 1 : 1 interaction, hydrogen-bonding capability, solvent-solvent interaction and solute-solvent interaction should be maximum in this region (60-80 wt.% of ethanol)¹.

The present state of our knowledge is yet inadequate to provide a satisfactory answer of the various problems associated with solution chemistry particularly the role of solvents on the dissociation constants of the ligands and their complexes. Systematic studies are necessary to make up the deficiencies.

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